

Ignorance is not bliss: The importance of publishing negative trials

Rujuta Saksena^{1*} and Janice M. Mehnert¹.

¹Rutgers Cancer Institute of New Jersey, USA

* Corresponding author, Email: mehnerja@cinj.rutgers.edu

It is not surprising that, in medicine, positive trials tend to generate more excitement compared with negative trials. Positive studies may be perceived as more likely to change the scope of one's clinical practice. In general, negative studies attract less attention from different parties, including authors, editors, peer-reviewers, physicians, and readers of medical literature. Indeed, industry sponsors and principal investigators may hesitate to publish negative studies if critical acclaim of the work is not anticipated.

Despite the sea of data that shows that positive studies are more likely to be published, it is crucial that we remember the importance of negative trials. This is particularly true in oncology, where the "stakes" of patients who suffer life-threatening disease are high and clinical research is already thwarted by its notorious expense and painstakingly slow pace. Dissemination of data arising from negative trials in this arena is arguably as important as the data from positive trials, particularly when publication of the negative results a) adds mechanistic insight to a therapeutic paradigm that is being studied by other investigators; b) yields information regarding the toxicity profile of a select agent or combination of agents that is not otherwise known or c) improves the understanding that negative results are in fact acceptable, and *able*, to be published, to avoid the perception of "pressure" to produce that may lead an investigator or sponsor to embellish results.

Manuscripts which focus on negative work need not hone in on the futility of their results. Rather, a productive manuscript shares the observations and interpretations of the investigators, but should comment further on how these understandings move the field forward and what information has been learned from the investigation. In oncology, such information is particularly useful when data shed light to the particular mechanism of action of a novel agent or approach, especially when the investigation is devoted to a rare tumor type or utilizes critical human tumor samples. It can be argued that it is the obligation of the scientific community to ensure that such studies, even if they did not reach their primary endpoint, should be published, especially when taxpayer money in the form of federal funding is utilized, or biomedical specimens are collected from participating patients who expect that their tissues will be used to further cancer research. However, perhaps the most

important and often overlooked consequence of not reporting negative studies is the unnecessary repetition of research by different groups in different countries, wasting time and resources. In this scenario, prior wrong hypotheses may continue to be held and tested[1], and opportunities to refine experimental approaches based on the findings of others are missed.

One of the most obvious disadvantages of the overpublication of positive results is that many treatments or exposures are overrated in the published literature. The underreporting of negative trials generates misleading conclusions about the effectiveness of treatments and a reduction in the power of systematic reviews or meta-analysis.

One of the most important advantages of reporting negative findings, particularly in the field of cancer research, is that such knowledge will lead to abandoning ineffective therapies. When ineffective drugs are used, unnecessary risks of drug toxicity are assumed and financial and human resources are wasted. If unexpected toxicities or novel pharmacokinetic findings are observed but not shared, there is no chance that these findings can inform studies of similar agents. There is also the false sense of security that the patient is being "treated," thereby denying or delaying other potentially effective treatments. Ineffective therapies also have long-term implications for the research and development of new drugs, as new drug development will either be delayed or not occur at all. This importance of sharing negative studies to directly inform clinical practice is similarly clear in the context of other medicine subspecialties as well as complementary or alternative medicine.

Finally, we cannot ignore the pressures felt by many within industry, academia and government to publish studies with impressive results. This approach, however, can dangerously skew the available medical literature. It is known that the publication of predominantly positive studies often leads to publication bias, which refers to the phenomenon that some studies have a greater likelihood of being published based on their results. There is a large body of data that supports the existence of publication bias in the medical literature, favoring positive trials.[2-11] Publication bias has been demonstrated in several cohort studies that followed up protocols approved by research ethics committees, trials funded by the National Institutes of Health, as well as abstracts presented at scientific

meetings.[3,4,9-11] In general, all of these studies have found that trials with significant or positive results were more likely to be published than those with non-significant or negative results.[2-9] Not only are positive trials more likely to be published, they are also more likely to be published earlier and more quickly compared to negative or neutral studies. The delay in publishing negative trials refers to “time-lag bias” and has been demonstrated in several studies.[2,9,12]

The source of publication bias stems from several parties, including study investigators themselves. Studies have shown that authors tend to submit trials with positive results for consideration of publication.[13] In addition to the excitement of sharing new results with the research community, “hot” publications may often lead to personal gain in the form of increased compensation, attention, or promotions. In an era of declining research funding across all spectra, it becomes easier to omit or delay publication of negative studies, particularly if the time and effort required to produce the “negative” publication is seen as a diversion of resources from other projects with more attractive results. With such studies that show researchers as more likely to submit reports with positive results, the assumption may follow that journals may be more eager to publish positive studies. However, this is less clear in the literature. Researchers may simply assume that reports of research with negative results will be rejected.[14] A study by Dickersin et al in 1987 suggested that non-publication was primarily a result of failure to write up and submit the trial results rather than rejection of submitted manuscripts.[14] Another study by Olson et al, looking at publication bias in editorial decision making regarding submitted manuscripts, did not find a statistically significant difference in publication rates between those with positive vs. negative results.[15] Regardless of the driving forces of publication bias, it is easy to see how published articles, as well as reviews that incorporate them, could become unreliable and overestimate the benefits of an intervention. In a study by Cleophas et al, the authors argued that the selective reporting of clinical research is both unethical as well as unscientific.[1] Thus, it is important to continue publication of well-conducted trials, as this practice is crucial to provide a complete picture of the medical research that is available for interpretation, regardless of whether the results are positive or negative.

Although the dissemination of research findings is likely to be a biased process, there are several steps that can be taken to ameliorate this issue of selective reporting. The prospective registration of clinical trials and the endorsement of reporting guidelines may reduce research dissemination bias in clinical research. In fact, trial registration has been a notable recent step in combating the underreporting of negative trials.[16] However, investigators may often query these registries to find that a particular study has been done, but no publication has resulted, or incomplete data are only available in abstract

form. Data from properly executed trials should routinely be made available, regardless of the nature of the results. Statistical tools such as sensitivity analysis modeling, funnel plot techniques, and probability models can be used to detect publication bias during a literature review.[2] The Cochrane Collaboration acknowledges the existence of publication bias in the systematic reviews it publishes and offers various ways to minimize this bias.[17] The impact of publication bias can be minimized after a literature review by confirmatory large-scale trials and by updating the systematic reviews.[2] Authors should be encouraged to submit manuscripts for publication, regardless of the nature of their results. Also, ethical committees and trial review boards can address the issue of publishing from their end. To maximize efficiency and acknowledge that the publication of negative results does require time, money, and journal space that could be devoted to studies with positive results, journals could revive the concept of a one or two page abbreviated report reserved for negative studies, designed to give readers the “bottom line” and to more widely disseminate information that otherwise would go unpublished or be relegated to abstract form only. Perhaps continued funding from private and federal sources should be contingent upon evident manuscript submission of all funded work. This is currently implicit in that investigators without a track record of publication may not receive further awards, but this does not deter investigators from prioritizing positive trials above negative ones. Finally, further research is needed to develop methods for qualitatively assessing the risk of publication bias in systematic reviews, and to evaluate the effect of prospective registration of studies, open access policy and improved publication guidelines.[2]

In summary, it is reasonable to conclude that the preferential publication of positive studies introduces imprecision into the assessment of health research and care, resulting in the dissemination of skewed, incorrect information, which could impede progress and at worst could lead to ineffective therapies and patient harm. There is abundant evidence to show that negative studies often go undetected, unreported, and unpublished.

The publication of well-conducted negative trials should be encouraged as the importance of negative trials in the current research context is exceedingly high, even if the results are not as spectacular as the investigators and sponsors had originally dreamed. To not publish a well-conducted negative trial is a violation of an implied contract on the part of the investigators and the funding agencies, but more importantly, of the implicit contract that exists with our patients, particularly those who give of their time and bodies to participate in clinical research.

References

1. Cleophas RC, Cleophas TJ (1999). Is selective reporting of clinical research unethical as well as unscientific? *Int J Clin Pharmacol Ther*, 37(1): 1-7.

2. Song F, Parekh S, Hooper L, Loke YK, Ryder J, *et al.* (2010). Dissemination and publication of research findings: an updated review of related biases. *Health Technol Assess*, 14(8): iii, ix-xi, 1-193.
3. Easterbrook PJ, Berlin JA, Gopalan R, Matthews DR (1991). Publication bias in clinical research. *Lancet*, 337(8746): 867-872.
4. Dickersin K, Min YI, Meinert CL (1992). Factors influencing publication of research results. Follow-up of applications submitted to two institutional review boards. *JAMA*, 267(3): 374-378.
5. Dwan K, Altman DG, Arnaiz JA, Bloom J, Chan AW, *et al.* (2008). Systematic review of the empirical evidence of study publication bias and outcome reporting bias. *PLoS One*, 3(8): e3081.
6. Dwan K, Gamble C, Williamson PR, Kirkham JJ; Reporting Bias Group (2013). Systematic review of the empirical evidence of study publication bias and outcome reporting bias - an updated review. *PLoS One*, 8(7): e66844.
7. Hopewell S, Loudon K, Clarke MJ, Oxman AD, Dickersin K (2009). Publication bias in clinical trials due to statistical significance or direction of trial results. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, (1): MR000006.
8. Ioannidis JP, Cappelleri JC, Sacks HS, Lau J (1997). The relationship between study design, results, and reporting of randomized clinical trials of HIV infection. *Control Clin Trials*, 18(5): 431-444.
9. Stern JM, Simes RJ (1997). Publication bias: evidence of delayed publication in a cohort study of clinical research projects. *BMJ*, 315(7109): 640-645.
10. Callahan ML, Wears RL, Weber EJ, Barton C, Young G (1998). Positive-outcome bias and other limitations in the outcome of research abstracts submitted to a scientific meeting. *JAMA*, 280(3): 254-257.
11. De Bellefeuille C, Morrison CA, Tannock IF (1992). The fate of abstracts submitted to a cancer meeting: factors which influence presentation and subsequent publication. *Annals of oncology : official journal of the European Society for Medical Oncology / ESMO*, 3(3):187-191.
12. Misakian AL, Bero LA (1998). Publication bias and research on passive smoking: comparison of published and unpublished studies. *JAMA*, 280(3): 250-253.
13. Sridharan L, Greenland P (2009). Editorial policies and publication bias: the importance of negative studies. *Arch Intern Med*, 169(11): 1022-1023.
14. Dickersin K, Chan S, Chalmers TC, Sacks HS, Smith H Jr (1987). Publication bias and clinical trials. *Control Clin Trials*, 8(4): 343-353.
15. Olson CM, Rennie D, Cook D, Dickersin K, Flanagan A, *et al.* (2002). Publication bias in editorial decision making. *JAMA*, 287(21): 2825-2828.
16. De Angelis C, Drazen JM, Frizelle FA, Haug C, Hoey J, *et al.* (2004). Clinical trial registration: a statement from the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. *N Engl J Med*, 351(12): 1250-1251.
17. (2013). Publication bias: the Cochrane Collaboration open learning material. <http://www.cochrane-net.org/openlearning/html/mod15.htm>, October 8.